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(Dis)composing Autocratic Dances in Brazil, in the Streets and on the Screens¹

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> Abstract

How do embodied practices inform us of the articulations of autocratic power? How do these practices create spaces of resistance and dissidence, spaces that not only respond to the dynamics of autocracy, but also aim at de-activating it? Neither below nor beyond power, embodied practices inform power by its own repetition. They inscribe and weave the materialization-dematerialization process of any sign, affect, *socius*, economy, and politics. In this context, dancing and choreographing stand out as practices that have been historically marked by the metaphysical and bourgeois aspiration for “autonomy,” “automobility,” and “free movement” within the ideological artistic field—in other words, they have been seen primarily as “Bodily Arts.”

In order to reflect on the complexity of these displacements, which I see as political displacements, I approach the emergence, dissemination, and erratic derivations of these practices as instances of *dancing-thinking*. This notion allows me to study dance as a form of embodied agency, politics, and knowledge, one which goes beyond its own artistic inscription and also beyond the subject-object framework of the modern colonial order.

> Keywords

Autocratic dances, dancing-thinking, embodied practices, baderna

> Resumen

¿Cómo nos informan las prácticas corporales de las articulaciones del poder autocrático? ¿Cómo crean estas prácticas espacios de resistencia y disidencia, espacios que no sólo responden a las dinámicas de la autocracia, sino que también pretenden desactivarlas? Ni por debajo ni por encima del poder, las prácticas encarnadas informan al poder mediante su propia repetición. Inscriben y tejen el proceso de materialización-desmaterialización de cualquier signo, afecto, *socius*, economía y política. En este contexto, la danza y la coreografía destacan como prácticas que han estado marcadas históricamente por la aspiración metafísica y burguesa de la “autonomía”, la “automovilidad” y el “movimiento libre” dentro del campo artístico ideológico; es decir, han sido vistas principalmente como “artes corporales”.

Para reflexionar sobre la complejidad de estos desplazamientos, que veo como desplazamientos políticos, me aproximo a la emergencia, diseminación y derivaciones erráticas de estas prácticas como instancias de *pensamiento danzante* (Andrade, 2016). Esta noción me permite estudiar la danza como una forma de agencia encarnada, política y de conocimiento, que va más allá de su propia inscripción artística y también del marco sujeto-objeto del orden colonial moderno.

> Palabras Clave

1 This essay is one of the outcomes of *Tele(Counter)Choreographies: Theorizing Dancing as Performative Practice*, a post-doc research held by Dr. Sérgio Pereira Andrade at Hemispheric Institute of Performance and Politics, New York University (2020-2022).

IdyM Vol. 04, N° 08, Año 05. Abril – octubre 2023 [03-24]
(Dis)composing Autocratic Dances in Brazil, in the Streets and
on the Screens / Sérgio Pereira Andrade
ISSN 2683-9318

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Danzas autocráticas, danza-pensamiento, prácticas encarnadas, baderna

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How do embodied practices inform us of the articulations of autocratic power? How do these practices create spaces of resistance and dissidence, spaces that not only respond to the dynamics of autocracy, but also aim at de-activating it? For the past few years, my research has centered on moving across the boundaries of philosophy and dance and performance studies in an attempt to respond to these questions. I have considered how such practices, in addition to repeating and rehearsing an ideological order, engage political agencies, propelling or opening them up towards the other, towards the vulnerability or the displacement activated by new practices—in other words, towards their own deconstruction.

Neither below nor beyond power, embodied practices inform power by its own repetition. They inscribe and weave the materialization-dematerialization process of any sign, affect, *socius*, economy, and politics. In this context, dancing and choreographing stand out as practices that have been historically marked by the metaphysical and bourgeois aspiration for “autonomy,” “automobility,” and “free movement” within the ideological artistic field (Bürger 1974; Hewitt 2005; Lepecki 2006)—in other words, they have been seen primarily as “Bodily Arts.” In the artistic realm, the aesthetic project is centered on the body as the medium-and-matter of such aspirations. However, as I argue, these practices circulate beyond the domains of the artistic paradigm—they are inserted in everyday routines, rituals, public demonstrations, and discourses.

Whether on a stage or in the streets, in private or public spaces, in books or on digital platforms/networks mediated by screens, dance and choreography mobilize, recruit, and disperse groups, signs and forces, and distribute space-time relations. People not only engage with dance in celebrations. They also employ it as *social choreography* — that Hewitt (2005) defines when “aesthetic operates at the very base of social experience” (3); when choreography is “ideological by virtue of what it both produces and instills rather than for what it reflects” (16) — and, I argue, as dis-rational and dis-locational agency by following and deviating from normalized codes, allowing or denying other people, machines, money, desires, and so on, to pause and/or move forward or backwards, materializing the disjunctive experience. In order to reflect on the complexity of these displacements, which I see as political displacements, I approach the emergence, dissemination, and erratic derivations of these practices as instances of *dancing-thinking* (Andrade, 2016). This notion allows me to study dance as a form of embodied agency, politics, and knowledge, one which goes beyond its own artistic inscription and also beyond the subject-object framework of the modern colonial order.

With the notion of dancing-thinking, I follow the deconstruction philosophy of Jacques Derrida. In *Penser à ne pas voir*² Derrida suggests:

Thinking is not reduced to reason, nor to knowledge, nor to consciousness; there is unconscious thought, there is irrational thought, there is a thought without knowledge: Kant distinguishes very strictly between the order of the thinkable and the order of the knowable. I can think, *denken*, of many things that I may not know. (...) When Heidegger wonders What do we call thinking? (*Was heißt Denken?*), “What does it mean to think?”, we previously know that for him thought is not reduced to science, nor to reason, nor to

² Here I am using the Portuguese edition. Cf. Derrida, 2012.

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philosophy. (...) Thought is also thinkable in a movement whereby it is a calling to come, it calls, it calls us, even if we don't know where the call is coming from, what the call means; it calls. (2012: 74-75; my translation)

For Derrida, *penser* (thinking) is one of the most obscure and enigmatic notions, a blind spot in any vocabulary which can have different semantic underpinnings in its translation from one language to another. This perspective informs my idea of the singularity of thinking as dance, or of that form of thinking that comes as dancing. This kind of thinking does not hold itself hostage to philosophy and can even question and provoke ruptures in philosophical thought, without trying to exert any authority over philosophy. As Derrida says, the possibility to question philosophy, to go beyond philosophy, “does not mean that a painter or a film director [or, if I may add, a dancer, a performer, a choreographer] has the means to question philosophy, but that what she or he creates becomes a carrier of something that cannot be controlled by philosophy” (Derrida, 2012: 47). Through his dialogue with Heidegger’s philosophy, Derrida reminds us that “thought is also thinkable in a movement whereby it is a calling to come”, this means, an opening up of force into deferential space-time, an event. Thinking would be a “question of hospitality,” neither below nor beyond meaning—in other words, thinking does not need to have a teleological meaning. Derrida thus proposes thinking as a sort of “receptive spatiality,” a notion linked to his work around *subjectile* and *khora*³—the latter one of the etymological roots of choreography.⁴

Derrida’s work further shows that thinking is also the movement of “going beyond,” a sort of exorbitant spatiality. Thinking, therefore, can be a displacement, a calling for a movement that comes, a telematic architecture of the transference of forces, a fugitivity, or even a postponement of the most diverse technologies of capture—such as reason, consciousness, the unconscious, knowledge, meaning, science, and philosophy. In his perspective, thinking is constituted by dragging things through space—which, according to the Argentinian dance philosopher Marie Bardet, is a characteristic shared by dance and philosophy as experiences (2014). This is what Derrida has called “*la atopie* or *la folie de la danse*” [the non-place or the folly of dance], its “revolution” (1992: 100).

Derrida formulated these ideas in an interview with Christie V. McDonald, titled “Choreographies” (1982). Discussing “the feminine” question in the philosophical field, the author attempts to critically counter the question, “how would you describe a woman’s place?” Reflecting on the famous statement by Emma Goldman quoted by McDonald at the beginning of the interview—“If I can’t dance, I don’t want to be part of your revolution”—and also on what Derrida sees as the revolutionary time created by women’s movements, he offers: “The most innocent of dances would thwart the *assignation à résidence* [the assignation to the

3 In *Forcener le Subjectile* (1986)—translated as *Enlouquecer o Subjétil* (1998) in Portuguese—Derrida writes: “Place, separation and receptacle, difference, interval, interstice, spacing as the *khora*: neither sensitive nor intelligible, nor the mimetic copy of the paradigm of *eidos*, nor the paradigm itself or the model itself, rather a ‘third genus’, difficult to conceive in any other way than by a hybrid ‘bastard reasoning’, as if ‘in a dream’, says Plato in *Timeo*, in a dream but beyond all sensation. This anesthesia does not mean that the *khora* is intelligible. It remains, as *subjectile*, underneath, and this is how it deserves its name of receptacle: *hypodokhé*” (Derrida, 1998: 110-111).

4 As Susan Foster points out: “The word ‘choreography’ derives from two Greek words, *choreia*, the synthesis of dance, rhythm, and vocal harmony manifest in the Greek chorus; and *graph*, the act of writing. The first uses of the term, however, are intertwined with two other Greek roots, *orches*, the place between the stage and the audience where the chorus performed, and *chora* [or *khora*], a more general notion of space, sometimes used in reference to a countryside or region. Where *choreia* describes a process of integrating movement, rhythm, and voice, both *orches* and *chora* name places” (Foster, 2011: 17).

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domestic space], escape those residences under surveillance; the dance changes place and above all changes *places*. In its wake they can no longer be recognized” (Derrida and McDonald, 1982: 69). For Derrida, the attribution of places is the very history of Western metaphysics—both as a topological question (what is the place of woman?) and as an economic question (because it all comes back to *l’oikos*, home, *maison*, *chez-soi*, the self, and the law of the proper place). This is what prompts him to think about Goldman’s dance as a turbulence, as a series of “incalculable choreographies,” as he says (76). As I have argued elsewhere, dancing-thinking in Derrida’s argument emerges as a resistance to the topo-economic concern of the “small European space of phallogocentric heritage” (Andrade, 2016: 192).

This leads us towards an understanding of the revolution of place as a mode of dancing-thought that resists the notions of domination, knowledge, field, place, and residence. It puts into tension the institutionalization of philosophy and the idea of thought as philosophical property. Derrida (2002) also works on the *right to*⁵ the declaration of philosophy as a field without horizon: “Philosophy has no horizon if the horizon is, as its name suggests, a limit, if the ‘horizon’ means a line that surrounds or delimits a perspective” (Derrida, 2002: 16). This is a radical position on philosophy as a “*yes to thinking*,” that is, “admitting the thinking, practicing and experiencing of a ‘right to philosophy’ without resorting to a certain assumption or essence of philosophy” (idem) or, I may add, an ontology or a genealogy of the subject.

The oscillation by the Derridean neither/nor marks a resistance against the formation of a genealogy or a subject of thinking that gathers around objects, a community of thought (like philosophy), or even an epistemology that would direct the exercise or practice of the ‘yes’ while thinking. It is a question of resisting the *straight movement*, the allegorical journey towards reason which is presupposed by the limit or the reach of its gaze in a horizon of possibilities. Here, I could say that Derrida advances a queer deconstruction method to interrogate “objectivity,” “clarity” and “straight” formulations of philosophical questions like “what is...?” or “what does it do?”

Taking the radical, anticolonial route paved by black studies, Fred Moten offers another provocative understanding of what we can understand as dancing-thinking. In *Blackness and Governance*, Moten writes:

But blackness still has work to do: to discover the re-routing encoded in the work of art: in the anachoreographic reset of a shoulder, in the quiet extremities that animate a range of social chromaticisms and, especially, in the mutations that drive mute, labored, musicked speech as it moves between an incapacity for reasoned or meaningful self-generated utterance that is, on the one hand, supposed and, on the other hand, imposed, and a critical predisposition to steal (away). In those mutations that are always also a regendering or transgendering (...) and in between that impropriety of speech that approaches animality and a tendency towards expropriation that approaches criminality, lies blackness, lies the black thing that cuts the regulative, governant force of (the) understanding (and even of those understandings of blackness to which black people are given since fugitivity escapes even the fugitive) (2013: 50).

According to Moten, the work of blackness in the arts requires “anachoreographic reset,” a bodily experience that situates the aesthesis of fugitivity and counter-spacing: a “critical predisposition to steal (away)” ... “lies the black thing that cuts the regulative, governant force of (the) understanding”. In this passage, the author marks a political strategy could be seen as an experience of dancing-thinking with (not about) the work of art towards the violent gesture of expropriation, dragging things away from “clarity,” away

5 Here the title is playing with both meanings of the phrase “*droit à la*” in French, as “*direito a*” in Portuguese, which refers to both a straight movement and an institutional practice (rights, laws).

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from the reasonable governance of meaning as something already there as elucidating “art”, as an object of modern aesthetic. It is a strategic engagement in blurring choreographies to reset them as anachoreographies. In *Black and Blur* (2017), Moten seems to materialize such resetting process in his dialogue with *Librettos*, by Charles Gaines, a 12-part body of work that brings together the score of the opera *La Vida Breve* (c. 1904) by Spanish composer Manuel de Falla (one of the leading names in the Nationalist Movement in early 20th Century), and a fiery 1967 speech by the civil rights activist and Black Panther Party member Stokely Carmichael.

By his own listening and walking through the Gaines’ installation, Moten says:

This blurring of score and speech and the breathing that takes place in the space between the objects’ layers instantiates new musical composition in choreographic performance, a kind of improvisation manifest in movement-activated visual and aural attention that occurs under what might be called temporal distress. I think of the visual-choreographic-musical blur induced by and given in *Librettos* as an entanglement of books in which what it is to quit (pay; clear up) and what it is requit (repay; settle a debt) are all bound up with a politics and an erotics of the incomplete and the unrequited. I’m interested in what can’t be finished or cleared up, the unpayable debt, the unaccountable, which is scored in our performance of Gaines’s work (2017: 248).

For Moten, Gaines’s work reveals and also insists on performing the anachoreographic resetting that is paradoxically achieved through the viewer’s listening walk, its own visual-choreographic-musical blur in the gallery. “Blur is the alternate process, [for] performing discomposition” (idem) between what is there, paid and repaid—the proliferation of relations amidst the orchestrations of materials, the appeal to sound, scores and speech acts by Carmichael and Falla, and what always persists as not enough because it is an unpayable debt⁶, unaccountable, unfinished—the history of brutality, colonial violence and long-standing anticolonial struggles. Through this uncomfortable zone, the blurring sensorial body situates right there, and not sufficiently there, the bridges of temporal distress that cannot be fulfilled—again, not even as art. It is in the failure of a *not enough, even as art*, blurring what has been announced as dance or not, or even dragging dancing-thinking away from the “Art system” where my research situates its practice. Moreover, I believe such Moten’s distributive and liberation blackness evokes incalculable counter-attacks to blur both the “transparency” (Spivak, 1999) of any discourse, transcendental meaning and the everyday agenda of anti-blackness.

This dancing-thinking allows me to blur both dance and performance beyond the boundaries of the artistic field, and even the necessity to have a field, but without denying that artistic practices have given us as “critical moves” (Martin), or have allowed us to build scores, diagrams and models of embodiment and performative practice. It gives space to a kind of hermeneutical(-and-sometimes-dramaturgical) tool⁷ that enables us to bring forth the relationship between dance, thought and politics. Something as Martin argues like: “dance arises through the mobilization of participation in relation to a choreographic idea” (4). While this sense of “putting something in motion” is an insightful connection to the work of politics, I would like to advance this analysis (with-and-) beyond the signs of movement and mobilization. I am more interested in

6 In another root, the *unpayable debt* is also discussed by Denise Ferreira da Silva as the state of symbolic and total violence, authorized and justified by the juridical-economic system that negatively accumulates a world implicated between the colonial, the racial and the capital, a “deep implication (the quantum level of entanglement) of everything that happened and it is yet to come in space-time existence” (Ferreira da Silva, 2019: 152).

7 And I will call such dancing-thinking, more specifically, as tele(counter)choreographies later on.

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thinking (as a discomposition) of how the emergences, displacements, quotations, diverse materials, forces, calls, translations and other supplementary gestures (in the name) of dances do, produce, and act as a situated politics, rather than the idea (whether it's choreographic or not).

Specifically in this essay, I follow this route in order to elucidate how the current Brazilian ultra-conservative turn (a turn that resonates with the larger geopolitical context) has moved through discourses, public demonstrations and screens, setting the political-democratic ground on fire. In the first part, I analyze the different uses of the term “baderna,” a speech act (Austin) compulsively reenacted by the State and conservative media to criminalize urban dissident movements. The uses of “baderna,” I argue, are a performative rhetoric gesture that historically has moved between dance, politics, and the colonial history of the country. In the subsequent section, I show how neo-fascist movements apply choreographic methods to disseminate their ideology and mobilize collective fear through the streets and networks mediated by bodies and TV screens, cell phones, computers, and other digital devices.

I. *Baderna* and the failure of white democracy

The myriad of street demonstrations that have taken place across Brazilian cities since June 2013—protests against the rise of bus fares, against gentrification, anti or pro-impeachment protests, and so forth—differ in many aspects; however, they all share the urgency of demanding the right to the city as a political spatialization of democracy. The right to the city, as described by Henri Lefebvre, is the prerogative of participating in the processes of urbanization which determine ways of life—forms, functions, and structures (affective, economic, political, cultural etc.)—as well as more vital anthropological needs of accumulating, spending or even wasting energies on a global scale (Lefebvre, 2001: 103). In this sense, the notion of the right to the city “is far more than a right of individual or public access to the resources the city embodies” (Harvey, 2014: 28); it involves claiming “some kind of shaping power over the processes of urbanization and presupposes to do so in a radical and fundamental way” (30). In *Rebel Cities* (2014), Harvey also reminds us that cities have always arisen “through geographical and social concentration of a surplus product,” defining urbanization as a class phenomenon “since surpluses have been extracted from somewhere and from somebody, while control over the use of the surplus typically lies in the hands of a few” (30).

When people gather in the streets and squares, when they move and talk to one another, claiming participation in a certain public space, they are not occupying a place previously designated for them in the city. Rather, they are claiming their right to rearrange the distribution of the social collective, the very corpus of participation in the democratic game. They are reimagining the urban politics according to their deepest desires. Indeed, as Judith Butler argues in “Bodies in Alliance and the Politics of the Street” (2011), despite the fact that these movements depend on the prior existence of pavement, streets, and squares, “the collective actions collect the space itself, gather the pavement, and animate and organize the architecture” (Butler, 2011: n.p.). Therefore, these groups remind us that the material elements that shape and mobilize what we call a city, and democracy itself, are co-implicated and in dispute with one another.

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Image 1: "A Batalha da ALERJ" [ALERJ Battle], by Rafael Fortuna Barão (Rio de Janeiro, June 2013).

In the Brazilian context, street demonstrations have made visible how cities are spaces of conflict and antagonism, challenging the false assumption that cities are peaceful and consensual spaces. Nevertheless, public debate has been massively focused on the discussion about the legitimacy of the movements and their organizational tactics. Generally, to the degree these street actions are radically opposed to the interests of the oligarchies and the neoliberal actors that regulate the concentration of the city's surplus, they are promptly labeled as criminal, uncivilized, delinquent, and as a huge and indistinct *baderna*. *Baderna* is a local, colloquial, rhetorical construction in Brazilian Portuguese, used always accusatively, and it is not easily translatable into other languages. *Baderna* designates people, actions, or events which are outside the rules of the game, and which, because of that, are deemed a menace to the continuity of a common ground that guarantees democratic participation. In its daily use, the phrases *que baderna!* [what a baderna!] or *isso está uma baderna!* [this is a baderna!] could be said by a policeman, a politician, a father or mother, a theater director, or any person in a position of authority, in order to mark that something is derailed or out of joint. In the social sphere, using this notion promotes the criminalization of dissident movements; in some cases, it can be equated to the English notions of "street riot" or "rogue."

The pervasiveness of the use of *baderna* in contemporary Brazil tends to disguise the history of the term, which is imbricated with the history of dance, with colonial politics and city politics. Indeed, few are aware that the term *baderna* derives from the name of the Italian ballet dancer Marietta Baderna, who immigrated to Brazil in the middle of the 19th century, at the peak of her artistic career. In the biography *Maria Baderna: a Bailarina de Dois Mundos* (2001), Silverio Corvisieri makes an important contribution regarding the blind traces of the history of this dancer whose name would be dragged into two main semantic streams: one concerning any kind of public disorder, violent confrontation, or riot; the other concerning any sort of group transgression.

There is no space here to offer a comprehensive historical survey of how the term *baderna* has transformed through time, up until its current status as a rhetorical weapon to criminalize social movements.

IDyM Vol. 04, N° 08, Año 05. Abril – octubre 2023 [03-24]
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ISSN 2683-9318

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Still, I would like to bring to the fore some genealogic key-marks within this trajectory which can enable us to think about how the recent urban disputes in Brazil are associated with what Derrida calls a “democracy to come”: “a meaning-in-waiting, still empty or vacant of the word or concept of democracy” (Derrida, 2009b: 52). For Derrida, democracy, in its dangerous contingency, is autoimmune—that is, structurally suicidal. This is a disturbing statement which reminds us about the vulnerability at the core of the word “democracy,” and also of doing and saying things “in the name of democracy.” Yet it is precisely this vulnerable quality which demands from us a vital state of messianism without redemption: “Democracy has always been suicidal and, if there is any future for it, it is in the condition of thinking differently about life and life force” (Derrida, 2009b: 88).

Marietta Baderna fled to Brazil in 1848, following the nationalist defeat and the harshening of the Austrian repression in Italy. Her arrival in Brazil was celebrated enthusiastically by her fans and is recorded in many articles and tabloids of the time, such as *Jornal do Comércio*, *Correio Mercantil*, and *Correio Braziliense*, which helped to invigorate the Baderna myth as a synonym of “grace and elegance in dance,” “angel and demon” (Corvisieri, 2001: 91). Between 1850 and 1851, the polemics involving her name and her dance in Brazil reached its height. In the city of Recife, Baderna was at the center of a heated argument regarding the foundations of slavery and the colonial establishment when she decided to include traditional Afro-Brazilian dances such as *fados*, *lunduns*, *umbigadas* and *baianos* in her performances at Teatro Santa Isabel. Furthermore, in Rio de Janeiro, Baderna became a frequent participant in popular street parties organized by free Black and mixed people. These dancing practices entailed a radical exercising of the right to the city:

[...] As Brazilians were plunging into a more austere time (the emperor of Brazil, D. Pedro II, would be later defined as “a Queen Victoria in long pants”), nobody should be surprised if such performances [both on the stage and in the streets], lead Baderna into an ever-widening disapproval among those Brazilians who fiercely aspired to an impossible racial purity, imitating slavishly the European manners and customs (Corvisieri, 2001: 40; my translation.).

However, in Rio de Janeiro, because of her overwhelming presence at the city’s balls, the dancer still attracted a legion of admirers, the so-called *badernistas*. This period came to be known as the era of *dancing fever* because of a growing wave of dance events in squares, salons, and other public spaces, which heavily divided the opinions of liberals and conservatives. This dancing fever period coincided with a yellow fever epidemic that took many lives all over the country, especially in Rio de Janeiro. Thus, those dance parties were considered contagion hazards; it wasn’t long until Baderna and badernista became synonyms with immorality or “caminho da perdição,” the road to damnation.⁸

Victor Andrade de Melo’s study (Melo, 2014) elucidates how Baderna’s interventions enacted a deviating force within the colonial body education associated with the dance fever during her time. By analyzing forty-seven articles published in the *Jornal do Comércio* between 1850 and 1851 by Brazilian statesman and influential journalist José Maria da Silva Paranhos⁹, Melo points out how body education through dance practices performed an important role in the aspirations of the Brazilian State, which became independent in

8 In those days it was believed that the yellow fever was transmitted by human contact—with all the racial undertones that this had at the time—and not, as it is the case, through mosquitoes. See Turco and Paiva, 2019.

9 Paranhos was also Minister of Foreign Affairs (1855-1857; 1858-1859), Minister of the Navy (1853-1855; 1856-1857), Minister of War (1871), and Minister of Treasury (1871-1875).

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1822. By mid-19th century, Brazil was beginning its post-colonial historical path, restructuring its aristocratic-bourgeois society, aligning the efforts of dance practices, educational agencies, and printed media to build the discourse of the ideal nation into the notion of civilization and progress.

The elites, who in the process of nation-building needed to recognize themselves as such, used the balls as a means of self-identification and differentiation. The balls were occasions when internal tensions were minimized, alliances and agreements were celebrated, and distinctions were marked between those who were outside (and also between those inside). Knowing how to dance had become a necessity. It wasn't about any sort of dance, but those styles considered civilized [waltz, polka, schottische, and redowa]. These ball practices could not be confused with popular practices, marking the reason why it was necessary to learn the correct way to dance (Melo, 2014: 757; my translation).

Melo analyzes many passages of Paranhos's texts in which the statesman enthusiastically fosters such colonial education through choreographic practices. However, Melo also highlights how Paranhos warned in 1851 that such practices should be exercised without excesses, to avoid the risk that dance become a dancing fever, a "corrosive poison of public morals, domestic happiness, and private wealth" (qtd. in Melo, 2014: 761). In another article, Paranhos went as far as to suggest that those women who partook in "the violent choreographic exercise of two, three, and six balls a week" would end up acquiring a bad face. For Paranhos, the excesses of dance—excesses that, lest we forget, were associated with popular parties and with Afro-Brazilian dances—"corrupt the good customs of a family or an orderly nation, excite greed, lead people to intrigues and baseness, and also gradually undermine the basis of probity" (qtd. in Melo, 2014: 761).

This kind of discourse influenced the reception of Marietta Baderna's interventions, which came to be seen as a deviation of the Brazilian nationalist-colonial order, an order haunted by racist and patriarchal values. "Dancing well" was ideologically associated with being "well educated" and "well disciplined"—with being a "good dance(r)"—in other words, with a very specific social choreography, a choreography to which badernas did not adhere.¹⁰ Through the act of invoking baderna, the oligarchies reified the limits that marked who belonged and who did not belong in the ball.

The commotion around the dancer's name and the aggressive public campaign against what the press called the "immorality" of the dance and its "libidinous excesses"—"excessive applause," "excessive cheering"—dragged Marietta Baderna into public repulsion and ostracism. This, as Corvisieri writes, led badernistas to enact thunderous protests against the outrage their beloved dancer was being subjected to, resulting in "preludes of physical confrontation that provoked police intervention and the indignation of the advocates of public order" (Corvisieri, 2001: 162).

Records of performances by Marieta Baderna in Brazil are found until the end of the 1850s. However, tabloids from later decades have increasingly popularized the reference to episodes of public disorder as being led by those "from Baderna" or "those usual badernistas." The repetition of this expression continued to appear in public discourse throughout the 20th century—not surprisingly, it was widely employed by the military dictatorship, especially after 1968—and continues to appear to this day, all of which has led to the

10 A "good dancer", in Althusserian parlance, would be a good subject interpellated by the law (Althusser 1971). I will return to this notion also informed by Lepecki (2006) later in this article.

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consolidation of a Brazilian political scene continuously haunted by the Baderna specter.

Given this brief historical account, I would like to propose to read “B/baderna” (both as a proper name and a rhetorical device) as an iterable speech act inserted in a process of “compulsive repetition.” In other words: Baderna describes, translates, or betrays an event that we have been shaken by, but cannot quite identify, determine, recognize, or analyze beyond the use of this very word: we call something or someone baderna or baderneiro in reference to the disturbance we define as such. If we consider compulsive repetition in Derridean terms, we can say that baderna as speech act is put into action in order to first, neutralize trauma by creating a distance from it, like a purge that says “go away, you baderneiro!” and then, as if by magic, to exorcize the thing itself, the fear or terror it inspires; and second, deny the thing as closely as possible from this act of language and utterance, in order to cover our inability to name, think, describe the thing (the disturbance it produces) beyond a referential normative circularity (cf. Derrida, 2003b: 90-93).

Following this idea, we can assume that the performative use of baderna reenacts a rhetoric/warlike resource in contemporary politics that singularizes—through accusatory speech acts—who are the outlaws. This structure of re-iterative and accusatory speech acts can also be related to the framework developed by Derrida regarding “rogue States” (*États voyous* in French), a notion deployed by the United States government any time a state does not follow its hegemonic order. According to this reiterative accusatory effort, rogue states are:

[...] delinquent states, criminal states, states that behave like brigands, like highway robbers or like vulgar rapsallions who just do as they feel, do not respect international right, stay in the margins of international civility, violate property, frontiers, rules and good international manners, including the laws of war (terrorism being one of the classic forms of this delinquency, according to the rhetoric of heads of sovereign states who for their part claim to respect international law) (Derrida, 2009a: 18-19).

Derrida also reminds us that *voyous* is translated into German as *schurken/schurkenStaat*, which can mean rascal, bounder, cheat, crook, rabble, blackguard, and criminal (19). In her Portuguese translation, Fernanda Bernardo uses the term *vadios* when translating *voyous*. However, in Brazilian Portuguese, this term—nowadays used to refer to bohemians and vagrants—has a very specific history linked to the criminalization of black people, especially those who do not work, either because of ideological refusal or idleness. The notions of “*Vadios and Capoeiras*” which appear as titles of Chapter 8 of the Penal Code of 1890 (signed into law two years after the abolition of slavery in the country) are defined as a contravention of moral and social-economic order by “failing to exercise a profession, office, or any job in which he earns a living, not having a means of subsistence and a certain domicile in which to live.” Specifically, the code most severely penalizes the practice of capoeira by “doing exercises in the streets and public squares of agility and body dexterity known by the name ‘capoeiragem.’”

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Image 2: “The Fairy of Baderna,” announces a headline of *Veja* magazine, in February 2014. This was a sensationalist article about the activist Elisa de Quadros Pinto Sanzi, broadcast by the media as “Sininho” (a Portuguese translation for “Tinker Bell”) who was accused, without any proof, of being the leader of Black Bloc tactics in the protests of June 2013. The image is a montage made by *Veja*, which put Elisa laxly walking through a Black Bloc action. It’s important to note that Eliza, who in Brazil is read as white, is wearing a t-shirt with a stamp of an iconic figure of Anastacia, an enslaved African descendent who lived in the country during the 19th century and was brutally forced to wear an iron muzzle all her life in Brazil. Making an odd and ineffective contrast, the t-shirt also reads: “The Favela Cannot Be Silent.” The perverse shuffled overlapping of Baderna, Sininho, Black Bloc and Anastacia in the same fictional image reveals how the white-oligarch media has performed the discourse of a failed democracy, mobilizing narratives that are always haunted by the reenactment of fictitious specters of terror by so-called outlaws.

Kowarick (1994) will also allow us to understand how the notion of “*vadiagem*” in the Old Republic (1889-1930) was used as an autocratic-eugenic rhetoric tool to implement the free labor class in Brazil. It designates the combination of “free and dispossessed” formerly enslaved black people and immigrants introduced in the country, resulting in an “uprooted mass that would be not incorporated in the productive process up to 1930, when the [Brazilian] economy achieved a higher degree of development and diversity” (Kowarick, 1994: 15). Later, after the folklorization of blackness in which capoeira was converted into sport (cf. Barbosa, 2007), the notion *vadio* started to gain a particular kind of “positive” value, to the point that today, a protest, a riot or political dissidence, or even a threat would not easily be called “a thing of *vadios*” or “*vadiocracia*” (to use the translation suggested by Bernardo to Derridean notion of *voyoucratie* as a kind of exercise of counter-sovereignty). I believe that the consequences of this shift of value of *vadio* can be understood as a reiteration of the undead “myth of racial democracy in Brazil” (Schwarcz, 1999). This is aligned with the idea of a “new passing renaissance” in the era of neoconservative post-racial language (Dawkins, 2012) which, using a kind of pacific-euphemist exaltation of “*vadio*” and “*capoeira*” (e.g. in promotional strategies that emphasizes the multi-racial discourse disseminated by UNESCO

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patrimonialising), hides and protects the structural interpellation of colonial violence.¹¹

This is why I would argue that in Brazilian Portuguese, *voyou/voyous* should be strategically understood as *baderna/baderneiros* as a way to emphasize the violent dynamic of these interpellations as *passing*, a rhetorical reiteration which materializes the project of democracy (and its vacant meaning) as aligned with a specific agenda of antiblackness. I am aware that such a deviation is beyond Derrida's project. "Baderna" as a performative accusation freely circulates from mouth-to-mouth, through papers and screens due to its ambiguous act of passing as color-blindness (Dawkins). In Brazil, the word circulates as an uprooted performative strategy, like a model of transparent meaning (as everyone knows what a baderna is) to designate, from the pure act of language (Derrida), what is an unacceptable social choreography. Nevertheless, this assumption carries a historically subversive feminine fugitivity, a memory of a "poison dance," a "detractor dancer." Such performative use always invokes a kind of failed attempt to form an obedient, civic and neutralized white choreography of how to live pacifically (with "no excesses of dance") in the city, always haunted by some fictionalized specter of blackness that derails.¹²

By arguing that *baderna* is *quasi-analogous* (and the hesitation here is deliberate) to the Derridean *voyou*, I emphasize how this repeatable and accusatory act of language is aligned with an international (neoliberal) order of building a vacant meaning of democracy, of managing ongoing stages of endless debt, as an embodied Brazilian memory of colonial passing. The performative use of the term neutralizes and negates what/who comes to disturb and also designates the dissident forces that cannot/will not take part in the public space according to the hegemonic and colonial place of enunciation. By act of language, those who are marked as "out of the game" are yet determined as non-tamable under the choreography of white governance and its will of [passing as] clean, pacific, well organized, straight sovereignty.

As Carl Schmitt famously stated, "The sovereign is he who decides on the exception" (2005: 5). The sovereign founds the law and therefore determines who is an outlaw. According to Derrida, the sovereign is structurally placed as an outlaw himself for he is the only one who can, by right, suspend the law by his own decree, by his force of law—and this, in fact, guarantees his indemnity. The sovereign can behave as an outlaw within the circularity of law. In *Voyous* (2003a), Derrida underlines the authoritarian contradiction of this reason, reminding us that Robert Litwak, in 2001, soon after the 9/11 attacks, justified the United States' national security plan and its vigorous offensive against rogue states by declaring: "A rogue State is whoever the United States says it is" (qtd. in Derrida, 2009a: 183). The US war against terror is justified by resorting to a sovereign speech act. This way of acknowledging the other by expelling them is also a way to justify the producer of the utterance as the strongest one. This takes us back to *baderna* as a political speech act: who decides when to refer to something or someone as *baderna* or *baderneiro(s)*? And also, what effects does this decision produce for political action?

11 Dawkins (2012), at the appendix of her book, offers some clues as to understand the category of passing within and beyond racial boundaries. I would highlight two them: "Passing is the invention and interaction of rhetorical personae—the passer's acceptable persona, the dupe, and the in-group clairvoyant or fourth persona" (159); "Passing reveals whose identities are valued as property, how much they are worth, and what defensive dupes will do to protect them" (160), and "Passing is an ongoing and eloquent drama of becoming more racially and rhetorically sincere" (idem).

12 We have seen some kind of this effect in the fictional media reenactment on *baderna* threat in the Image 2. Also, the study of Solano et al (2014) on the Black Blocs of São Paulo tells us something about this haunting dynamic. The authors identify the presence of the symbolic universe of the periphery/favela as a kind of discourse or concept, "not a geography," widely spread among the youth who performed Black Bloc tactics during the protests; however mostly of them were middle class and white university students. Black people's effective absence in the massive protests of 2013 and 2014 was also identified by Vargas (2018: 153): "this absence suggests lingering effects of structural antiblackness that even supposedly popular and sweeping movements are not willing or able to address, much less redress."

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In 2016, at the outset of the Olympic Games and three years after the intense street demonstrations that challenged the capitalist model of the city, the Brazilian government swiftly issued an anti-terrorism law. In Rio de Janeiro, in particular, the demonstrations were prompted after a popular uproar against the city's government, which, on the verge of bankruptcy, offered tax exemptions to public transportation companies at the same time that it elevated bus fares. Meanwhile, the constructions to transform Rio into an "Olympic City" were forcibly removing hundreds of people from their homes, including Indigenous and Black communities downtown—all in the name of "innovation." This modernization reflects the ideology of "creative destruction"—a neoliberal conceptual jargon that disposes the urban masses of every possible right to the city (Harvey, 2014: 59). The protests were designated as crimes against the public order and labeled as *baderna*. Accusations notwithstanding, Brazilians kept taking to the streets, pressuring the government to acknowledge their demands; meanwhile, the government—now authorized by a legal structure—armed and trained the police to violently repress street demonstrations. Furthermore, by enacting the exception through the utterance of "baderna," "baderneiros," "badernistas," the State, the media, and those holding power reinforced an urban choreography of sorts that replicated the neoliberal/neocolonial movement to keep producing and consuming its surpluses of colonial violence.

By analyzing the performative use of *baderna* in this scenario, we must observe the role of this particular generation of protests and the ways of which the state's management of fear operates through bodily subjection. Thomas Hobbes argues in his *Leviathan* (1965): "Of all Passions, that which enclineth men least to break the Lawes, is Fear. Nay, (excepting some generous natures,) it is the onely thing, (when there is appearance of profit, or pleasure by breaking the Lawes,) that makes men keep them" (Hobbes, 1965: 229). For Hobbes, mastering this "nature of men" is a requirement for sovereign power. The sovereign must not only know how to make the law—a *savoir-faire*—but also demonstrate, by the strongest force (if necessary) the consequences of being an outlaw. Demonstrating his own expertise in power is the *faire-savoir-faire*, the power of the master of "giving a lesson" (Derrida 2009b). That means that white sovereignty does not work only by repressing what it fears, but also by performing, by demonstrating, how power can incorporate this fear.

Following this route, we could say that, more than an artistic promise or commitment, the inscription of the choreographic in political demonstrations works as a paradoxical pedagogical exercise of sovereignty. Here we can look to the *Orchesography* treatise and its fabulous anecdote of the lawyer that begs to learn the art of dance following the master's demands. During the dialogue, Capriol demonstrates himself aggrieved by a double fear: fear of the mortality of the dance master and fear of himself (a lawyer, a man of the law) to be reproached by society "for having the heart of a pig and the head of an ass" (Arbeau, 1995: 17)—in other words, fear to be a beast, an outlaw, a *baderneiro*. Here we find a tiny rift in the structure of sovereignty. Right there, at the end of 16th century France, where and when the geopolitical boundaries of the colonial reason of State were being drafted, choreography appears as a method of *savoir-faire* for ordering a sort of healthy social life by following a well-oriented and well-paced dance. In this passage, Arbeau ties up two of the primordial taxonomic *savoir-faires* of dance: the first, "employed in war for the strength and defense of the State," and the second, "the virtue of attracting hearts" (Arbeau, 1995: 18). There is a very specific expertise of composing, controlling, and assembling forces in the choreographic in order to associate, by attracting and loving, and to deny, by war, strength and defense. This *faire-savoir-faire* touches on the ethical limit of the political: it also enacts and creates friendships and enmities, the similar and the dissimilar.

Although a very repressive onto-theological mark remains in its structure, sovereignty traverses the time

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that lies at the core of the political, choreographing it. Sovereignty is an ambivalent practice that is at the foundation of any right: on the one hand, it gives the sovereign the power to choreograph a force which attains the efficacy of a right, on the other, the materialization of this force through its choreographic enactment, gives us the power to question the sovereign. By being activated by a choreographic performance, an iterable structure, the sovereign exposes itself to its own deconstruction.

II. The Choreography of Everyday Neo-Fascism is Fear

Judith Butler has argued time and again that the body lies at the core of disputes about the democratic game. In her contributions on the Arab Spring, Butler states: “the political claims are made by bodies as they appear and act” (Butler, 2011: n.p.), bodies which are “themselves modalities of power, embodied interpretations, engaging in allied action” (Butler, 2011: n.p.). Therefore, one can say that on the advent of that which is “democratic,” coextensive with that which is political (Derrida, 2009b), the political-democratic to come is always in dispute, and it demands a demonstration and an inscription in the city pavement itself. Following Butler, when people gather on streets and in squares, when they move together and demand their right to participate in massive demonstrations, these events pave the political-democratic space through bodies-in-struggle: “a struggle (...) over those basic ways in which we are, as bodies, supported in the world—a struggle against disenfranchisement, effacement, and abandonment” (Butler, 2011: n.p.). Given this, one can easily understand the increasing need for a choreographic perspective within analyses of the performativity of public demonstrations.

Indeed, it is my argument that there is always a choreographic dispositive in any demonstration in the public space—even if this event is not being choreographed by trained practitioners of dance or performing arts. Arranging bodies, strategies, roles, movements, desires, alterities, and so on, the choreographic works as an iterative and decentered way of inscription of embodied power. Following Butler’s theories of subjection (1997), we could say that choreographies of protest evoke the ambivalent power of agency. Butler says: “Painful, dynamic, and promising, this vacillation between the already-there and the yet-to-come is a crossroads that rejoins every step by which it is traversed, a reiterated ambivalence at the heart of agency” (Butler, 1997: 18). Between something which already-there and that which yet-to-come, choreographies are a powerful device to engage the political subject in the contended public space.

Here, it is of utmost importance to note that in Brazil, as in other national contexts, the streets of major cities have been paved not only by the traditional rallies of trade unions, political parties, and progressive social movements; these streets have also been assaulted by massive marches organized by far-right movements, led by traditional oligarchies, neoliberal businessmen, and leaders of Neo-Pentecostal churches. Whether left- or right-wing, from a choreographic perspective, these demonstrations evoke the democratic *ethos*, which guarantees the right to protest—even when the protest asks for the interruption of the failed democratic system.¹³

This is why in this final section I turn to consider one such notable case: the choreographies by the far-right Fortaleza city group “Consciência Patriótica” (CP). Starting in 2016, CP disseminated videocalls on

13 One can evoke here, for example, the many demonstrations which have asked for military intervention and/or to the return to dictatorship; also, the 2019 initiative by President Jair Bolsonaro, who convoked people to a public demonstration against the congress and the STF (the Brazilian Supreme Court) “in the name of democracy,” as he said without blinking.

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social media convoking people to gather in favor of the impeachment of President Dilma Rousseff, and then again in 2018 in the context of the presidential elections, to support Jair Bolsonaro's campaign. In 2016, the main slogans of these calls were "Be a Patriot" and "out Dilma, out Lula, out PT"; and in 2018, "Don't let Brazil turn into Cuba," "Don't let Brazil turn into Venezuela," "We are all Bolsonaro, *tamo junto!*" (We are together)."¹⁴

If we analyze the first video of the series, *Be a Patriot – Tutorial*¹⁵ we notice that the choreographic interpellation works through a dance of "spontaneous nationalism" by convoking flash mobs in public places throughout the country. These videos show yellowish-green digital avatars that enact a choreography inviting people to get together in order to fight for "their nation" and to throw out Dilma, Lula, and the PT [Workers Party] all at once. "Out Dilma, out Lula, out PT!" they scream as they dance. Through the choreographic, their call says that anyone can enact the protest: children, youth, and old people, anyone who follows step-by-step the combination of dancing, singing, rhythm, and a "patriotic consciousness" of sorts, which is the organizing signature of the group.

Of course, following Susanne Foellmer, we could be skeptical and think of this choreography as "merely pretentious in the face of the social engagement of those who were demanding" (Foellmer, 2016: 63) the impeachment of Dilma and the end of the rule of the PT in Brazil. But these were not mere jokes—those involved protested and spread the performance across the country, dancing *Be a Patriot* (in the streets and on the internet) as a political act. I do not, however, want to evaluate the effectiveness of *Be a Patriot* as a mere enactment of an ideological structure where a teleological cause brings a determined political effect. In Foellmer's analysis about actions choreographed by Ehud Darash in the context of Occupy Wall Street, she points out: "the question is whether an action like this [a choreography of protest] actually creates political awareness or rather remains in the sphere of a purely artistic project, which is using the described counter-public as a place of experimentation" (63). Her analysis is driven by an understanding of the choreographic as a medium of protest, which organizes and transfers "(system) elements that fluctuate between the everyday, the artistic, and the political" (63). However, from my perspective, the choreographic analysis should contribute to move us beyond the splitting between "political awareness" and the "purely artistic project." In this, I follow Jacques Rancière, who warns us about the risk of falling into the dichotomy between art and politics, which is anchored in the "Illuminist model of action and empowerment through knowledge" (Rancière, 2008: 73).

Indeed, the *Be a Patriot* call situates us within a different, very radical, route. The instigators of the performance do not define themselves as an artistic collective or a part of the counterculture, something that could bring forth the specter of the discussion between "art and non-art"—an ontological issue profusely debated in contemporary art, which has also haunted Dance Studies, as Foellmer reminds us. Performing an uncritical use of dance, that is, a performance with no pretention of commenting on or critiquing the dance field, *Be a Patriot* evokes only the very general "Brazilian patriotic identity." The digital avatars, which become something like a generic figure of anyone, with their yellowish-green dresses and pants, appeal to all—"at the school, the college, even at the gym [...] groups of Brazilian children, youth, or old people: schedule a demonstration on the square, in the street or at the beach of your city and be a patriot." And even if they sign their collective as "patriotic consciousness," actually, they do not need to instigate any awareness of a political subjectivity to make the choreographic demands work.

¹⁴ This last slogan is performed along with the choreographic gun hand gesture.
¹⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=JaKQxNR2E_8

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It is my contention that choreography's activation doesn't require an intuitive subjectivation—a kind of subjectivation that remains in the territories of both Kantian transcendental subjectivity and the Husserlian phenomenological approach, which binds presence and intuition as a continuum, and also binds political action to decision, consciousness and responsibility in the illuminist subject. In contrast, we can follow the Derridian perspective on *writing* as a way to reframe the choreographic which goes beyond any intuitive subjectivation.

In “Signature Event Context” Derrida argues, “For a writing to be a writing it must continue to ‘act’ and to be readable even when what is called the author of the writing no longer answers for what he has written, for what he seems to have signed” (Derrida, 1988: 8). According to this perspective, the performativity of writing works as iterability, “the working out of the logic that ties repetition to alterity” (7), which is bound to nonpresence in general (of the author, his present intention or attention, the plenitude of the desire of meaning, the wish to communicate, and so on) and also to a disseminating movement (the movement of *différance*). Derrida describes the bidding of iterability, nonpresence, and dissemination in this way: “the essential drift [*differ*] bearing on writing as an iterative structure, cut off from all absolute responsibility, from *consciousness* as the ultimate authority, orphaned and separated at birth from the assistance of its father” (8). For the philosopher, this binding is the only radical condition of writing, it is its law. By performing this binding, any writing act inscribes its own ipseity, its own force of law.

Following Derrida's formulations, one of André Lepecki's most important contributions to dance studies has been to bring forward a specific genealogy of choreography as masculinist-embodied writing.¹⁶ In *Exhausting Dance*, Lepecki explains how the concept of choreography emerges in Western dance tradition in order to “remachine” the body so it can “represent itself as total ‘being-toward-movement’” (Lepecki, 2006: 7), a dispositive which requires “a yielding to commanding voices of masters (living or dead), [...] submitting body and desire to disciplining regimes” (9). On his analysis of Thoinot Arbeau's *Orchesographie* (1589), the first choreographic manual written in the West,¹⁷ Lepecki shows how *writing* was adopted by the field of dance as a resource to support the solipsistic work of the dancer even at a distance from his master. Thus, choreographic writing becomes “a technology of transportation, more precisely of tele-transportation” (27). Lepecki also highlights the fact that the first manual of choreography in the Western tradition was written as a homosocial deal between two men of law: a priest, Thoinot Arbeau (the dance master), and a lawyer and mathematician, Capriol (the dancer disciple). These male characters are not there by chance, they inscribe choreography as a writing calculated by the law, a “lawful dance” in Lepecki's words. Thus, choreography carries in its own ontopolitical archive some sense of sovereignty expressed by the foundation of the copula command-obedience to/of the law in the form of “dancing well.”

Although the argument of writing as a “technology of teletransportation” retains a somewhat logocentric logic that closures writing as continuity, symmetry, and as a support for an intuitive subjectivity, Lepecki's contribution is important to my argument given that his rigorous study offers a synovial connection, so to speak, between the choreographic, writing, and sovereignty. It is important, however, to insist on writing's radical binding of iterability, nonpresence and dissemination in order to reaffirm why a choreographic protest does not require, at all, any authority of political consciousness to be able to act. This binding is a (counter)spacing-timing, a necessary autoimmunization structure that enable us to think another kind of sovereignty, a sovereignty that is not an absolute and indivisible force.

16 I am mostly referring to the Lepecki's initial works, *Inscribing Dance* (2004) and *Exhausting Dance* (2006).

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In order to inscribe its force of law, the sovereign exposes itself to the movement of *différance*, to its deconstructive force. This is very clear in the case of the *Be a Patriot* performance. Even if no one had gone to “the square, the street, or the beach” to perform the dance, *Be a Patriot*, as a choreographic-writing dispositive, is already acting and paving political ground, and always deviating from the initial command of the master-choreographer-avatar voices. So, if choreography is a (intentional or not) medium of transferring and imprinting a force, as a movement of writing it is also an opening that weakens its own pretension of “unity” and “indivisible” self-power. This repetition of alterity, the counter-spacing-timing which constitutes the effectiveness of the choreographic, exposes it to its own deconstruction, revealing it as a *tele(counter)choreography*.¹⁷ This reframing does not ask for a new concept of choreography. Rather, the central point here is to highlight the performativity of the choreographic as radical writing, that is, to highlight the way in which choreographies take part in the dynamics of power as a transmission of embodied and “exbodied” performances. It is only because choreographies, without exception, harbor tele- and counter-displacements that they can reshape their gestures, strategies and effects on the political ground, either to reproduce or to resist, to bow to power or to deviate from it.

This ambivalence can be seen also in the 2018 videos of *Consciência Patriótica*, at a time when the group was heavily engaged in the presidential campaign of Jair Bolsonaro. The group produced two new choreographies—[Brasil Acima de Tudo, Deus Acima de Todos](#) [Brazil Above Everything, God Above all] (Bolsonaro’s official campaign slogan) and [Bolsonaro é 100% Brasil](#) [Bolsonaro is 100% Brazil] (geared specially to address residents of the Brazilian north and northeast, who usually vote for candidates of left-leaning parties). In contrast to the 2016 video, the dancers in these new videos were real people, not digital avatars, with their faces painted.¹⁸ The level of choreographic complexity is different as well because this time it called for stronger bodies with some dance training. In the choreographies staged in different public spaces of Fortaleza, Sao Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, and other cities, the group repeated some of the steps

17 I have been working with the notion of telechoreography since my PhD dissertation (2016), as a kind of “draft thought” to address the process of embodied and erratic displacements of the dancing-thinking that I discuss here. From this first formulation, I have been experimenting with different ways of nominating such disruptive force through my own praxis, combining writing, teaching, studio practice and collaborative efforts. One of most nourishing encounters was my partnership with Lidia Larangeira’s work on different levels and stages. In her work she has demonstrated how the choreographic technology “has tried, not without resistance, to master the female through the subjection of sociability (and sexuality) towards to the field of male heteronormative desire” (Larangeira, 2019: 32, my translation). In an attempt to propose ways of escaping and confronting this legacy, Larangeira and I started to experiment with practices of counter-choreographies that have generated different artistic collaborations. A few examples are the piece *Brinquedos para Esquecer ou Práticas de Levante*, which was performed in different formats between 2016-2019 and the course *Performance as Counter-Choreography and Situated Inscription* at MAR Museum, during the Trans-In-Corporados conference, which invited students, researchers, artists and activists to reflect on and exercise collective practices of resistance in the gentrified Rio de Janeiro’s port zone. Later, Larangeira wrote: “countercoreography is not a decree to end choreography, it is not a campaign against choreography, it is not an anti-choreographic struggle, but an attempt to produce “dances” by deactivating old uses and significant traces that reproduce consecrated and naturalized ethical-political values. Counterchoreographies aim to render the traditional modes of organization and production of choreography inoperative by betraying the legacy through new ways of acting” (idem, 56). On the other hand, the notion of telechoreographies, as I have mentioned, has always been referring to the situated process of materialization and dematerialization of dancing-thinking, the in-ex-corporeality without which no sign, concept, object, thing, question, blurring or discomposing operations could take place, distancing from its supposed “original” inception. It is a counter-spacing instance, radical alterity moves. That is why at some point in 2019, I started to adopt the “tele(counter)” graft in the attempt to redraft (again) this writing of counter-sovereignty force.

18 A kind of passing as reenactment, which quotes some memory of “*caras-pintadas*” manifestations, in 1992, formed mostly by students who painted their faces with the colors of Brazilian national flag to demand the impeachment of the former-president Fernando Collor de Mello.

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performed in the videos from 2016, while also incorporating new elements related to the presidential campaign. One of the new gestures incorporated in the 2018 choreography was the gun hand gesture, a central symbol of Bolsonaro's campaign, singularized towards the loosening of gun legislation in the country, one of the most important goals of his platform. This gesture was cheered and choreographed by the majority of voters that year.

Image 3. Gun gesture, the choreographic symbol of Bolsonaro's campaign.

Bolsonaro and his followers used a creepy yellowish-green choreography, in which, among other steps, they moved their extended arms up and down with their hands doing the gun gesture. These poses and finger gun-shots, with cameras and cell-phones, digitized in pictures and videos were compulsively shared through social media along with the hashtags “#mito,” “#somostodosBolsonaro,” “#estamosjuntos,” among other slogans which engage their pharmacopornographic economy (Preciado, 2013). Dressed in yellow and green colors, extremely excited-frustrated bodies appear in the videos, shaking their rifles-arms and calling Brazilians to participate in patriotic struggles for gore politics (Valencia).

These choreographies of fear dance to a masturbatory rhythm, creating self-pleasure through lots of excitation and lots of frustration. They call for their right to exert violence in the streets and on social networks, banalizing and naturalizing it. “Mito! Mito! Mito! Mito! Mito!”, they chant, performing the always already resented virility of a mythical past supposedly destroyed and constantly under threat.¹⁹ These movements of masculinist necro-empowerment are reproduced and disseminated in the fascinating glow of the flowing passage between hands, fingers, hashtags, lethal, and non-lethal weapons in all possible platforms, on the floor, on helicopters, on drones, on the Internet, and in the relation established between neighboring windows, between bodies in the city.

Right after the election, the normalization of the hand-gun gesture continued to mingle in the Brazilian political debate—in protests against Congress, against the STF, and against Bolsonaro's opposition—without ever being labelled as “baderna.” As a quotidian gesture, the hand-gun became a recurrent meme over the internet, appearing even in birthday paraphernalia (see [here](#) and [here](#)), feeding an economy of images produced by cell-phones and shared on social networks. In Rio de Janeiro, the choreography of guns was also performed by the genocidal governor Wilson Witzel who, alongside professional snipers,

¹⁹ For a critical reading on articulation of discourse of fascism, which evokes the patriarchal mythical past, resentment subjectivity, and sexual anxiety, see Stanley (2019)

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boarded helicopters to shoot the favelas and poor people from above, while mediatizing his performance on social media as a way of threatening and regulating the state (see [here](#) and [here](#)).²⁰

During an interview with *The Intercept Brazil* while he was in prison in 2019, President Lula da Silva also resorted to the symbol, but this time with a twist (see the exact moment [here](#)):

[...] The only thing that you see is everyone making this gun gesture with their fingers all the time [playing the little gun gesture with his own hand], and this is actually the same shape they used before to make an “L” for Lula [making a twist of the axes of his index and thumb fingers into the form of the letter “L”]. I guess Bolsonaro borrowed this gesture [the fingers gun] from when it was used [the L’s Lula sign] in my presidential campaigns (Lula da Silva 2019; the comments in parenthesis are mine).

How should we think through these iterative horrifying choreographic moves? What remains and what deviates in these reenactments? Is Lula tensioning the limits of populism by proposing Bolsonaro’s and his followers’ choreography as an inversion of the choreography of his own government? These are questions will keep spinning here. However, I would like to note that the choreographies of fear engendered by the current neofascist moment in Brazil are definitely tied to neocolonialism (as historical reiterations of the uses of baderna and its clear relation with the colonial project and the creation of the bourgeois Nation-State) and neoliberalism (when those choreographies are encouraged in order to justify or create austerity policies). The trap of the “neo” factor mobilizes the repetition of an old ultra-conservative dynamic system that at each historical conjuncture appropriates the accumulated layers of technologies in order to amplify its bodily subjection terror and mitigate any possibility of rupture.

The gestures of the “finger pistol” and “gun in hand” have been the main signs of greeting and adherence to Bolsonarism. In addition to the multiple examples I have cited so far, we can say, without hesitation, that dance and choreography in Brazilian neo-fascism are fundamental tools for shaping its warmongering body politics. I would even say that dance and choreography in Brazilian neo-fascism are strategic gears of a historical war machine that, from embodied practices of engagement and annihilation, triggers the “sacrificial structure of preventive counter-revolution”, as Safatle (2020) put it.

In Florestan Fernandes’ *Bourgeois Revolution in Brazil* (1970), at the pinnacle of the military dictatorship in the country, the author defined the Brazilian state as “a strong rational association between capitalist development and autocracy,” marking the 1964 Coup as a “preventive” response by the bourgeoisie to the social conflicts of the period (Mattos). For Fernandes, when boasting about “defending the stability of order,” as the military did, they were reiterating Brazil’s ruling class commitment to the reactionary project aimed at legitimizing bourgeois domination, which also was, as we saw, embodied by colonial choreographies. This project, as with all dictatorships in Latin American, was part of the global resonance of the cold war, marking Brazil as the periphery of dependent capitalism, that is, capitalism necessarily subordinated to the autocratic and imperial order of the global North, in other words, a neocolonial order.

The period of re-democratization after the dictatorship did not change this main dynamic of reenactment;

20 The episodes marked the very concrete borders of the structural racism performed by the State. According to official information from the Rio de Janeiro Public Security Institute, in the first year of Witzel administration, police operations in Rio de Janeiro City killed 1,814 people, 1,423 of whom were Black and Brown (see <https://glo.bo/2Ac0saD>). In front of the cameras, Witzel would declare: “the more good citizens with firearms we have to protect society, the better for us”, “the police will aim at the head” and “the mess is over”

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instead, the neoliberal state has deepened this neocolonial subalternity that, in turn, has prepared the historical material ground for the outbreak of neofascism. Thus, the current process of exhaustion of neoliberal presumptions such as the “humanization of capitalism,” “class conciliation” and “multiracial identity” have had direct implications for the political bodies that make our state of *passing as democracy*.

In the last 30 years, we have witnessed social majorities made up of the marginalized sectors of the population being subjected to various embodied technologies of rationing (in the sense of programmatic scarcity) democracy. “This programmatic rationing stirs up the civil war and instigates the constitution of the machine of production of internal enemies” (Centelha, 2019: 45). The list of civilian enemies produced by this historical process of *passing* is immense and crosses several spectra: the black and indigenous Brazilians, communists, union members, the unemployed, LGBTQIA+ communities, feminists, drug users, strikers, homeless and landless people, the hooded youth, the Black Blocs... the “baderna” and the “baderneiros” in general.

While we might be perplexed and ask ourselves how we got to this pinnacle of programmatic, recordable and transmissible horror through different technologies, bodies and platforms, we should make the effort not to dismiss them, label them as ridiculous, childish or even unimportant manifestations. These multiple embodied practices are mechanisms in a kinetic-kinesthetic project without which no power or political body would be able to move or mobilize. The reiteration of choreographies of fear, hatred, and incitement to war are fundamental. They manage an economy of desire and self-pleasure, preparing embodied inter-subjectivities, without which no sovereign power would perform its own failure domain and unpayable debt.

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 IDyM Vol. 04, N° 08, Año 05. Abril – octubre 2023 [03-24]
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on the Screens / Sérgio Pereira Andrade
ISSN 2683-9318

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